

The transcriptome and epigenome of the marine calanoid copepod *Acartia clausi* after short-term cadmium exposure

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Introduction

- **Integrative studies** linking molecular, subcellular, organismal responses to pollutants remain scarce; → yet are crucial for establishing mechanistic links between early molecular and higher-level biological responses.
- **Cadmium** is particularly harmful due to its high toxicity, persistence, and bioaccumulation potential.
- Aim: to **systematically evaluate the effects of short-term (48 h) exposure** of the copepod *Acartia tonsa* to cadmium at the pre-established EC20 concentration (nominal 238.8 µg Ca L⁻¹).

Physiological response

- Left: **activity of the antioxidant enzyme glutathione S-transferases (GST)**: significant difference between control and exposed group (Welch's t-test, $p > 0.05$).
- Right: indicator of **lipid peroxidation and oxidative damage** via assessment of thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (**TBARS**) formation: no significant effect (Welch's t-test, $p < 0.05$).

Epigenomic response

- **Global methylation** via colorimetric ELISA approach (left): No significant difference in average global 5-mC DNA methylation between exposed and control treatments (Welch's t-test, $p > 0.05$).
- **Locus-specific methylation** via Whole Genome Bisulfite Sequencing (WGBS) analysis still ongoing

Differential gene expression

- **Cadmium** resulted in weak differential gene expression in *Acartia tonsa* after 48 h with only 47 DEGs identified (FDR < 0.05)

- **Upregulated GO:** enriched for carotene catabolic processes and oxidoreductase activity.
- **Downregulated genes** mainly involved redox processes and glutathione S-transferase functions.
- **Downregulated GO:** enriched for lipid homeostasis, ion binding, oxidoreductase activity, and metabolic pathways.

Conclusion

Acartia tonsa exhibited limited physiological and transcriptomic responses to cadmium exposure. No significant effects were observed on lipid peroxidation, oxidative damage, or global cytosine methylation. In contrast, GST activity was significantly affected, a response supported by transcriptomic analysis, suggesting activation of detoxification pathways rather than widespread molecular disruption.

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